

Molecular Rearrangements in the Microbiological Transformations of Terpenes and the Chemical Logic of Microbial Processes

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Oxygenative and prototropic molecular rearrangements, observed during microbiological transformations of terpenes are discussed. The former which have been noticed during the metabolism of mono- and sesquiterpenes by *Aspergillus niger* NCIM 612, have been studied with the aid of cyclohexene, 1-methylcyclohexene, 4-methylcyclohexene and tetralin as model compounds. Prototropic rearrangements have been observed during metabolism of terpenes by *Pseudomonas* species isolated by enrichment culture techniques. They are pinene to 1-*p*-menthene conversion, involving rupture of a cyclobutane ring in the bicyclic system, rearrangement of camphene to isborneol and conversion of an acyclic terpene to a monocyclic one. These studies have revealed that the presence of a single extra enzyme often enables the microorganism to thrive on different substrates.

THE microbiological transformations of mono-terpenes have led to the discovery of several interesting molecular rearrangements, most of which are ionic in nature. These rearrangements, classified broadly into oxygenative and prototropic rearrangements are brought about by common fungi and bacteria respectively. Although fungi are unable to grow on terpenes as the sole carbon source, the cell mass derived in the presence of common energy rich materials can oxidise and metabolise terpenes to carbon dioxide and water. On the other hand, the bacteria isolated on the terpenes as the sole source of carbon may be expected to degrade these molecules by the most efficient energetic pathways in order to derive the maximum amount of energy within the limitations of enzymatic and genetic make-up of the cell.

The Oxygenative Rearrangements

These rearrangements have only been observed with common fungi, particularly *A. niger* NCIM 612 which has shown remarkable versatility in the hydroxylation and oxygenation of mono-, di-, tri- and tetra-cyclic mono- and sesquiterpenes¹⁻⁵. Some examples are shown in Chart 1. Three types of oxygenation reactions have been observed:—(a) Ionic addition of water across the double bond such as the formation of α -terpineol (IV) from limonene (I). (b) allylic oxygenation, observed in the formation of *cis*-carveol (II) from limonene (I), (+)-*cis*-verbenol (VII) and (–)-*cis*-verbenol (XI) from (+)- α -pinene and (–)- α -pinene respectively and (–)-pinocarveol (XV) from (–)- β -pinene (XIV) and (c) oxygenation on a double bond with rearrangement exemplified by the formation of (+)-2,8-menthadien-1-ol (V) from limonene, (+)-*trans*-sobreol (IX) from (+)- α -pinene (VI), (–)-*trans*-sobreol (XIII) from (–)- α -pinene (X), (–)-myrtenol (XVII) from (–)- β -pinene (XIV) and the alcohol (XIX) from α -santalene (XVIII).

In order to study the underlying mechanisms in these oxygenation processes, model compounds were employed^{6,7}. These are shown in Chart 2.

Allylic hydroxylation was observed in all these cases similar to that seen with most monoterpenic substrates. A new reaction was however observed, the hydration of a double bond to yield 1-methylcyclohexanol (XXIX) from 1-methylcyclohexene⁷ (XXVI). The other instance where this reaction was observed was in the conversion of limonene (I) to α -terpineol (IV).

Interestingly, while cyclohexene (XXII) and 1-methylcyclohexene (XXVI) gave optically active monohydroxylated products (XXIII) and (XXVII), 4-methylcyclohexene (XXX) and tetralin (XXXIII) gave the corresponding racemic allylic alcohol (XXXI) and (XXXIV) respectively.

The only interesting oxygenative rearrangement which was observed in the model compounds was the formation of the optically active *cis*-3-cyclohexene-1, 2-diol (XXIV) from cyclohexene⁶. The reaction of cyclohexen-3-ol (XXIII) with V₂O₅ and hydrogen peroxide also yields diol XXIV⁸ and gives a clue to the probable mechanism of its formation microbiologically. In compound XXIII, the alcoholic oxygen may provide one of the ligands which coordinates with the pentavalent vanadium. One of the probable modes of formation of the diol (XXIV) is through a six-membered transition state involving a liganded peroxy polyvanadate (XXXVI) as depicted in Chart 3, the driving force being the formation of the resonance stabilized polyvanadate anion.

Alternatively, it can be visualized that first a β -epoxide is formed and this is then opened along with

Chart 1 : Metabolites isolated from the action of *A. niger* NCIM 612 on some terpenes.

Chart 2 : Metabolites isolated from the action of *A. niger* NCIM 612 on some model compounds.

Chart 3 : Probable mechanism for formation of diol by the action of V_2O_5 and H_2O_2 on cyclohexen-3-ol.

migration of the double bond to give the diol (XXIV). It is not easy to rule out *a priori* the epoxy intermediate in the enzymatic double bond oxygenation processes with rearrangement in the fungal system. A cyclic mechanism, however, becomes more attractive if one attempts to unify the active oxygenating species involved in both types of fungal hydroxylations—oxygen insertion at the allylic position and at the double bond. In this process, one has to reconcile two opposing trends, namely, preservation of chirality of the allylic oxygen entering the molecule observed even with cyclohexene (XXII) and 1-methylcyclohexene (XXVI) and the racemisation process observed with 4-methylcyclohexene (XXX) and tetralin (XXXIII).

The biological hydroxylation of steroids and some aromatic compounds have been classified as "mixed function oxidases"⁹ in which one of the atoms of the oxygen molecule is directly introduced into the substrate along with the simultaneous reduction of the other atom to water by a reducing agent such as NADH, FADH₂, NADPH etc.

In all probability, the only feature common in the V^{5+} and hydrogen peroxide system and the fungal system may be the involvement of a 5- or 6- membered transition state leading to a stereospecific introduction of a second hydroxyl group on an adjacent carbon atom in a cis-disposition to the first in either system. Then mechanisms for the second hydroxylation in cyclohexenol (XXIII) can be visualized involving either of the two species Enzyme- FeO^+ and Enzyme- FeO_2^{2+} as shown in Chart 4. The formulation of Enzyme- Fe^+-O^+ from Enzyme- $Fe^{2+}=O$ may be justified from the observed behaviour of the higher oxidation states of the transition metals which tend to withdraw the outer valence electrons into the inner shell. The highly electrophilic oxygen can then withdraw electrons from the neighbouring double bond in the transition state (XXXVII) causing an allylic shift. In the resulting intermediate (XXXVIII) the Fe^+-O^- bond can readily ionize to regenerate Enzyme- Fe^{2+} and the diol (XXIV) after protonation. Regarding Enzyme- FeO_2^{2+} a six membered cyclic transition state (XXXIX) analogous to (XXXVI) in V^{5+} and H_2O_2 system may be visualized.

Chart 4 : Mechanisms for hydroxylation at a saturated carbon atom.

In allylic hydroxylation also both these species can be implicated. One can visualize two types of mechanisms here : (a) A concerted one in which the electrophilic oxygen forms single electron bonds with both carbon and hydrogen as in the intermediate (XL) (Chart 4). A general electronic shift strengthens the C-O bond at the expense of the C-H bond leading to an insertion of oxygen. Alternatively (b) the electrophilic oxygen can cause a hydride abstraction from the sp^3 carbon to leave a high energy or hot carbonium ion (XLI). The hot carbonium ion, still with sp^3 geometry can react instantaneously and specifically with the neighbouring hydroxyl released from the Enzyme- Fe^+-OH , by an instantaneous ionisation process due to proximity effect, before it has a chance to collapse.

In case however, other stereoelectronic factors accelerate a rapid delocalization in the hot sp^3 carbonium ion to a collapse in the planar sp^2 stage (cold), the carbon moves out of phase from the hydroxide released from the enzyme and can react with other hydroxyls in the medium. In such a case the product would be racemic. Thus the formation of racemic 3-hydroxy-4-methylcyclohexene (XXXI) from 4-methylcyclohexene (XXX) can be explained since the delocalization of the carbonium ion formed at position 3 is accelerated by the hyperconjugative effect of methyl group at position 4 and the electron cloud of the 1-2 double bond. Similarly racemic α -tetralol (XXXIV) formation from tetralin (XXXIII) can arise from delocalisation of the electrons of the benzene ring.

The above mechanism explains the observed data in fungal hydroxylation but requires rigorous proof. One way of proving a carbonium ion intermediate is to check if group migration occurs in a highly substituted carbon atom. A substrate such as (XLII) should also give rise to products such as (XLIII) and (XLIV). In case of a radical intermediate such methyl migration is unlikely. However, the limitations in such experiments are the acceptability of compounds such as

Chart 5

(XLII) to the enzyme. The other way of proving this mechanism would be by employing H_2O^{18} . In case of racemised products, there is likely to be considerable incorporation of O^{18} . However, due to feeble activity of the enzyme in cell-free systems, this proof has not been accessible so far.

Hamilton and coworkers have carried out extensive work on chemical models and mechanisms for oxygenases¹⁰. They noted¹¹ the similarity of many mono-oxygenase catalysed reactions to carbene and nitrene reactions and suggested that these enzymes catalyse their reaction by an oxygen atom transfer or oxenoid mechanism^{12,13}. Support for this mechanism has been obtained by the NIH group¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

Hamilton also is of the view¹⁰ that the oxygenation process proceeds through an intermediate which has some blend of radical and ionic character. The oxygen insertion will occur with retention of configuration if the transition state or intermediate collapses directly to products. The enzyme, by binding both oxidant and substrate could prevent separation of the intermediate into radicals or ions and give the alcohol directly.

The Metabolism of Terpenes in the Pseudomonas and Prototropic Rearrangements :

The Pseudomonas species isolated by enrichment culture techniques showed interesting prototropic rearrangements of bicyclic systems converting them into monocyclic ones and in one case an acyclic terpene to a monocyclic one. The bacterial systems are more convenient to work with from the enzymatic point of view and usually cell-free systems have moderate to high enzyme activity.

A strain of *Pseudomonas putida-arvilla* (PL-strain) isolated both from limonene (I) and (+)- α -pinene as the sole source of carbon was capable of growing on (+)-limonene (I), (+)- α -pinene (VI), (-)- α -pinene(X),

(-) β -pinene (XIV), 1-*p*-menthene (LIII), 3-*p*-menthene (LXXXV) and *p*-cymene as substrates. As no other carbon source is provided, the organism has to use these substrates as a primary energy source.

It was demonstrated by a series of experiments that the organism derives at least three two-carbon fragments ($CH_3CO-SCoA$) from the 10-carbon monoterpenoids. The remaining four carbons are obtained as isobutyric acid which is metabolised via methylmalonyl CoA to succinyl CoA. From limonene,^{17,18} the energy yielding pathway is initiated by a methyl hydroxylation to perillyl alcohol (XLV) which undergoes two NAD-specific dehydrogenations to perillyl aldehyde (XLVI) and perillic acid (XLVII). Perillic acid (XLVII) or more probably its CoA derivative is converted to a β -hydroxy acid (XLVIII) by a crotonase-type reaction. A dehydrogenation then follows to the transient β -keto acid intermediate (XLIX) leading to the dicarboxylic acid, β -isopropenyl pimelic acid (L) which by two successive β -oxidations yields(LI) from which the third two-carbon fragment is released yielding methacrylic acid (LII) (Chart 6),

Chart 6 : Pathways of degradation of limonene and 1-*p*-menthene.

The pathway from 1-*p*-menthene (LIII)^{19,20} was parallel to that from limonene involving intermediates (LIV-LVI) with saturated isopropyl side chain and isobutyric acid (LVII) and three two carbon fragments. It is probable that isobutyric acid or its CoA derivative is dehydrogenated to the methacrylic acid derivative which gets hydrated and dehydrogenated to yield methyl malonyl CoA.

The passage of 3 moles of two carbon fragments through the Krebs cycle yields 36 moles of ATP and succinate metabolism yields another 24 moles of ATP per mole. Some more moles of ATP must also be formed in the alcohol and aldehyde dehydrogenations en route from terpene hydrocarbons to 3 moles of acetyl CoA and

one mole of succinyl CoA. For e.g. from limonene, this would be another 18 moles. The total energy liberated from a 10-carbon terpene hydrocarbon would then be 78 moles of ATP or 7.8 moles ATP/mole carbon. This is comparable to that obtained from glucose (38 moles ATP/mole of glucose or 6.3 moles of ATP/mole carbon).

In the metabolism of the bicyclic monoterpenes such as (+)- or (-) α -pinene and β -pinene, the micro-organism needs one step to convert these into the p-menthanoid skeleton for the degradation of which it has an efficient machinery. The fungal system which converts α -pinene to *trans*-sobreol through an oxygenative rearrangement has been discussed earlier. In studies with *Pseudomonads* no oxygenative rearrangements which can proceed by protonation of an epoxide to yield a carbonium ion has far been encountered. Epoxidation, however, does occur in the bacterial system, for instance in the formation of the *trans* diol (LVIII) the hydroxy ketone (LIX) and the *cis*-diol (LX) from limonene by the PL-strain¹⁷ (Chart 7). These are side products that the strain does not metabolise further. On the other hand, among the products isolated from the fermentation of geraniol (LXI) by the *P. incognita* strain²¹ were the triol (LXIII) and the hydroxy ketone (LXIV) derived from epoxide LXII. LXIV is converted to 6-methyl-hept-5-en-2-one (LXV) which is metabolised further by a still unexplained pathway.

Chart 7 : Epoxidation reactions.

The degradation of geraniol through geranic acid follows the interesting mechanism put forward by Seubert²² which involves carboxylation of methyl groups and the elimination of the latter as acetic acid (Chart 8).

Three distinct types of prototropic rearrangements have been observed in the metabolic pathways of terpenes in *Pseudomonads*. The first one, pinene \rightarrow 1-*p*-menthene conversion is concerned with the rupture of a cyclobutane ring in a bicyclic system leading to a p-menthanoid skeleton. The second one, camphene \rightarrow borneol rearrangement is a conversion of one bicyclic terpene to another and third one converts an acyclic terpene to a monocyclic one.

(i) *Pinene-menthene transformation* : The *P. putida arvilla* strain (PL strain) brings about prototropic

rearrangements of both α - and β -pinene^{23,24} converting them both finally to the same enantiomer of 1-*p*-menthene involving a concomitant reduction.

Chart 8 :

Chart 9 : Pathways of degradation of α - and β -pinenes.

This rearrangement could not be demonstrated in cell-free preparations so far or in intact cells under nitrogen but the course of the rearrangement has been elucidated from the structure of the side products. The products borneol (LXVII), oleuropeic acid (LXX) and the hydroxy acid (LXXII) indicate the participation of the ions (LXVII), (LXIX) and (LXXI) respectively. (LXXI) is stereospecifically reduced to 1-*p*-menthene (LIII) in the case of both α - and β -pinene. The downstream products from 1-*p*-menthene has the same β -isopropyl geometry irrespective of whether they are derived from (+) α - or (-) β -pinene.

To account for the products and the lack of the protonation activity in the cell-free system, it was postulated that the protonation and subsequent carbonium ion rearrangements take place on the enzyme surface and the product is released only after the reducing agent has completed the task of hydride addition at position 4. Small amounts of the ion

(LXVII) can leak out and get neutralised and transformed into borneol (LXVIII).

One can appreciate the chemical logic of the organism, which by bringing into play one extra enzyme, pinene-*p*-menthene isomerase-reductase, can convert these bicyclic systems into the *p*-menthanoid structure which can be degraded by the common pathway. However, since the system requires the generation of a hydride donor such as NADPH or NADH, the reaction does not proceed under anaerobic conditions.

(ii) *Camphene-isoborneol lyase isomerase*: This reaction has been observed in another *Pseudomonad* (camphene strain) growing on camphene (LXXIII) as the sole source of carbon^{25,26}. It first converts camphene to isoborneol (LXXVI) by a prototropic rearrangement via the ions (LXXIV) and (LXXV). Isoborneol is then converted to camphor (LXXVII) which is then degraded through 5-exo-hydroxy camphor (LXXVIII), 2,5-diketo camphane (LXXIX) followed by two Baeyer-Villiger oxidations to yield the lactonic acid (LXXX) which is degraded further (Chart 10).

Chart 10 : Pathways of degradation of camphene.

This pathway is essentially similar to the one worked out by Gunsalus and co-workers^{27,28} for the metabolism of camphor by *Pseudomonas putida*, C₁B and C₅B. The camphene strain requires one extra enzyme to convert camphene to isoborneol. After this rearrangement, it can direct isoborneol into the more familiar pathway for camphor degradation. The camphene-isoborneol lyase isomerase has been demonstrated in the cell-free system in the particulate fraction. Interestingly enough, this enzyme also converts α - and

β -pinenes to α -terpineol (IV) by prototropic rearrangement although the organism does not grow on α - or β -pinenes.

(iii) *Prototropic rearrangement of acyclic to monocyclic terpenes*: The Strain of *Pseudomonas incognita* described earlier was isolated on linalool (LXXXI) as the sole source of carbon^{29,30}. Among the metabolites isolated from the fermentation of linalool by this organism was the monocyclic acid, oleuropeic acid (LXX). This is formed by hydroxylation of the 10-methyl group of linalool and the primary alcohol (LXXXII) formed is oxidised through the aldehyde (LXXXIII) to the corresponding acid, linalool-10-carboxylic acid (LXXXIV) by an alcohol and an aldehyde dehydrogenase successively both being NAD dependent. The acid now undergoes a prototropic rearrangement to lead to oleuropeic acid (LXX) and perillic acid (XLVII) (Chart 11). This organism also grows on limonene and follows a pathway identical to that in the PL-strain^{18,30}. Thus, by bringing into play one extra enzyme for the prototropic ring closure, the organism can degrade the molecule by the perillic acid \rightarrow β -isopropenylpimelic acid pathway.

Chart 11 : Pathway of degradation of linalool.

The studies bring out two important features: (i) Although microorganisms show great diversity in metabolising a large number of synthetic or natural compounds, the number of biochemical pathways are limited in nature and dictated solely by the logic of energy metabolism. (ii) Often the presence of a single extra enzyme enables the microorganism to thrive on diverse substrates.

The data is still insufficient to predict the biochemical pathways for the degradation of other monoterpene hydrocarbons. But it is possible to rule out some modes of degradation of cyclic monoterpenes. To illustrate the point one can take the case of the limonene skeleton as shown in Chart 12. Out of the three modes of ring cleavage, the second one is unlikely to occur as this gives odd fragmentation pattern of 5 and 3 carbons and only one 2 carbon fragment. The existence of pathway 3 is possible but not yet observed. In the metabolism of 3-*p*-menthene (LXXXV) by the PL-strain³¹ the organism introduces a double bond at 1,2 position through a hydroxylation at position 1 to give (LXXXVI). This is dehydrogenated to the

Chart 12 : Modes of cleavage of the limonene skelton.

diene (LXXXVII) and then the ring is eventually cleaved at 1,2 position giving the keto acid (LXXXVIII) (Chart 13).

Chart 13 : Pathway of degradation of 3-p-menthene.

Regarding the predictability of rearrangements from bicyclic monoterpenes to monocyclic, the data from the observed metabolism of α - and β -pinenes and camphene is insufficient. But some pattern is emerging from which it may be possible to exclude some speculative hypotheses.

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